

Article

Near-Real-Time Detection of Insect Outbreaks in Urban Trees Using a PlanetScope Time Series

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Abstract: A critical challenge for urban forests is the arrival of *Toumeyella parvicornis* (or pine tortoise scale) in Italy, as this species damages stone pine (*Pinus pinea* L.), an emblematic Mediterranean species. The aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of remote-sensing data for monitoring pest invasions in the urban area of Rome, using PlanetScope images with a 1-day revisit time and 3 m spatial resolution, making them ideal for detecting outbreaks in complex urban areas. First, we constructed a reference dataset, georeferencing 238 healthy trees in Tenuta San Rossore (Tuscany) and more than 2000 damaged trees in Rome's green areas. In any case, this dataset of healthy trees—obtained from forest areas—was expected to exhibit higher photosynthetic activity compared to urban green areas. Second, more than 30,000 PlanetScope images were analyzed to test the effectiveness of the Renormalized Difference Vegetation Index in detecting this specific forest disturbance. Finally, different thresholds were examined, allowing for the identification of an optimal threshold to discriminate healthy trees from damaged trees. The index results showed a marked drop during the summer in the infested areas, compared to the healthy areas. The identified threshold provided 99% accuracy in detecting infested trees. The approach applied in this study demonstrated that PlanetScope imagery proved effective in detecting *T. parvicornis*, leading to promising results.

Keywords: urban forest monitoring; remote sensing; *Toumeyella parvicornis*; invasive pests; vegetation indices

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1. Introduction

Vegetation cover, such as cropland, grassland, and forest, provides various benefits to ecosystems and humanity [1]. In particular, urban forests are important because they enhance the quality of life of urban residents by strengthening social connections and improving physical and mental health [2–4]. They also reduce air and water pollution and heating and cooling costs and increase real estate values while mitigating the impacts of climate change [5]. According to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, these benefits can be classified into three categories: regulation, provisioning, and cultural services [6].

Regulation services include air quality climate and water regulation, as well as pollination control. In contrast, provisioning services involve the supply of materials such as wood, fuelwood, and food products, whereas cultural services are relevant for recreation and ecotourism. The provision of ecosystem services makes the management and maintenance of forest areas important [7]. Italian cities—which are spread throughout different climatic, altitudinal, and latitudinal gradients—host a variety of tree species, including *Pinus pinea* L., which is particularly common in the largest Mediterranean cities, such as Rome. Monitoring *P. pinea* in Mediterranean urban environments is crucial due to its prevalence and representation.

The current management of these trees in the urban environment must also consider frequent falls (due to inadequate maintenance, pests, pollution, or incorrect planting), which are dangerous for both people and structures [8]. Particularly challenging factors include (i) proximity to heavily developed areas; (ii) problems related to forest structure and management; and (iii) climate change, which causes droughts and rising average temperatures [9]. Root development is significantly impacted by the proximity to roads and pavement. The growth of tap roots is consistently impeded due to the complex pedological conditions of compact and asphyxiated soil [10]. Continuous work on the road surface can permanently damage the roots, leading to collapses. Biotic and abiotic factors cause plant stress, making trees and forests highly vulnerable to fire and pests [11]. Moreover, climate change, as an anthropogenic factor, intensifies extreme environmental conditions that are expected to increase and significantly impact existing forests [12]. The potential effects of changes may interact with the dynamics of pest development in ways that are difficult to predict [13].

Particularly representative is the situation in Rome, where, in addition to increasingly warm and stressful temperatures for trees, a high anthropogenic density persists. At present, *P. pinea* forests are infested by the biotic agent *Toumeyella parvicornis* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) in Rome. This scale species originates from North America, and it has expanded to the Caribbean region and Europe [14]. It was first detected in Italy in 2014 and is under the official control of the EFSA Panel on Plant Health. This alien pest produces sticky honeydew related to feeding activity, which causes the development of sooty molds that cover branches and needles. Infested plants suffer yellowing, reduced growth, phyllotopsis, decline, and death [15]. In addition to the spread of this alien species across Europe due to globalized world trade, global warming is contributing to its proliferation [16]. At the end of 2014, the pine tortoise scale *T. parvicornis* was recorded in Naples for the first time [17]. The insect rapidly spread (specifically in the regions of Abruzzo, Campania, Lazio and Apulia), infesting stone pine trees, a species that is representative in the Mediterranean landscape. In 2018, *T. parvicornis* was also reported in Rome and led to the decay and death of many plants around Central and South Italy [18].

Monitoring insect infestations is a crucial element in safeguarding urban forests. The timely identification of infested areas allows for the implementation of targeted control measures, thus helping to limit the spread of invasions and minimize the associated damage [19]. The use of satellite-based monitoring for insect infestations is a fundamental approach to large-scale natural resource management [20]. This approach, which is particularly advantageous when considering remote or hard-to-reach areas where traditional ground-based monitoring methods may be impractical, is also useful in urbanized environments, providing standardized, high time-frequency data, allowing for the analysis of vegetation health status trends. By leveraging the ability to cover extensive areas rapidly and provide up-to-date data, satellite remote sensing facilitates the early detection of infestation signals [21]. Satellite monitoring of insect infestations utilizes high-resolution imagery and multispectral or hyperspectral data to identify changes in vegetation, such as plant decline or loss of foliage cover, which can indicate the presence of infestations [22].

Images from satellites, such as Landsat or Sentinel-2, with their global coverage, are commonly used for tree monitoring [23,24]. Relevant tools allow for the monitoring of infestation progression over time, aiding in the prediction of the spread of pests and the

planning of control actions [25]. However, the spatial resolutions of Landsat and Sentinel-2 are 30 and 10 m, respectively, and their temporal frequency of at least 5 days under cloud-free conditions may be a limitation for monitoring the progression of infestations. To overcome these limitations, PlanetScope images were used in this research. Planet Labs, Inc. operates PlanetScope, a constellation of microsatellites that collects high-resolution multispectral images in the visible and near-infrared (NIR) bands [26]. PlanetScope images offer a high spatial resolution (3 m) and a very short revisit time (1 day), features that make them extremely useful for vegetation and land monitoring. To test a georeferencing and radiometric correction method, Leach et al. [27] used PlanetScope imagery to identify changes in land cover. Francini [28] used PlanetScope to produce a near real-time disturbance alert system that could generate a new forest change map for each released PlanetScope image. Furthermore, in the forestry sector, Rösch [29] combined PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 images with other information layers to map the presence of mountain pine (*Pinus mugo* Turra) in the Sarntal Alps. PlanetScope imagery has also been used in agriculture by Shi [30] to map damage to rice crops. Even in the highly urbanized context of Zagreb, Croatia, PlanetScope images have been used to map allergen species in green areas [31]. Thus, its high spatial and temporal resolution represents a significant advancement compared to Sentinel-2 (10 m spatial resolution and 5-day revisit time) and Landsat images (30 m spatial resolution and 15-day revisit time). These characteristics make PlanetScope images extremely useful for numerous applications.

In this study, PlanetScope imagery was chosen, even considering the limited size of the urban areas to be monitored. The ability to work with more uniform pixels provides greater reliability. In Sentinel-2 or Landsat, the mixed pixel effect is too pronounced for this specific context [32], particularly in terms of relating remotely sensed data to georeferenced data surveyed on the ground. Remote sensing becomes more reliable when complemented by ground-based monitoring [33,34]. Usually, data are collected during field surveys, where specialized technicians manually inspect plants and gather information on insect presence [35] and the extent of the infestation. Despite its accuracy, ground-based monitoring has several limitations. It is labor-intensive and costly, requiring specialized personnel and considerable time to cover large areas [36]. Additionally, it is challenging to obtain a comprehensive view of the situation, as access to certain areas may be limited. Field surveys are also subject to human error and may not provide real-time data, potentially delaying the interventions necessary to counteract infestations. For this reason, in this study, field data were integrated with remote-sensing data, where ground data facilitate satellite analysis and enhance its specificity, while the remote-sensing data augment and complement the field data.

The aims of this study were (i) to evaluate the effectiveness of PlanetScope satellite constellation images to monitor damage caused by the infestation of *T. parvicornis* on *Pinus pinea*; and (ii) to identify the advantages and limitations of combining ground surveys and remote-sensing data for insect-outbreak detection, monitoring, and management in urban areas.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

This study involved the Rome municipality (Figure 1), which has a public space incidence of 3.7% (over an area of 1287.4 km²)—or approximately 48 km²—allocated among equipped green areas, historical archaeological parks, and large urban parks. Moreover, protected natural areas and nature reserves fall partially within the municipal territory.

Figure 1. Localization of sites for surveys (marked with grey circles the sites and marked in green the perimeter of the areas) and a detail of a surveyed area (Villa Borghese) with its georeferenced point.

The area selection for the surveys was a critical decision, as the study focused on a single tree species. The greater the extent of tree cover, the easier it is to recognize in PlanetScope imagery. Therefore, locations with extensive areas covered exclusively by pine trees were chosen. This selection was based on specific characteristics, such as canopy density and size. As a result, historic villas, some public parks, and other green areas (Table 1) were included in the study, as these spaces offered more uniform coverage of the same tree species. Large historic villas have the highest concentration of *P. pinea* (Figure 1).

All sites were selected within the area defined by Ring Road A90, the main road encircling the city of Rome, which is more densely populated and urbanized. Consequently, large green areas extending outside this boundary, such as Castel Fusano pinewood, were excluded.

Table 1. A list of the locations visited, accompanied by dates of surveys and plants surveyed within each area. The ones with * were selected for the analysis.

Location	Name of Area	Number of Trees	Number of Suitable Trees	Date of Survey
Latium region, Rome	Parco degli acquedotti *	130	126	16–29 June 2023
	Villa Ada	30	30	21 June 2023
	Parco Don G. Alberione	16	16	23 June 2023
	Villa Borghese *	340	332	21 June–29 July–27 August 2023
	Green area via D. Campana	10	9	7 June 2023
	Via delle Terme di Caracalla *	106	91	17 June 2023
	Parco G. Sbragia *	47	47	23 June 2023
	Parco E. Corizza	16	16	6 June 2023
	Villa Glori *	202	193	21 June–22 July 2023
	Villa Lazzaroni	37	37	18 June 2023
	Parco Papacci *	49	49	10 June 2023
	Villa Pamphili	574	528	27 June–11 July–23 July–28 July–10 August 2023
	Parco Petroselli	19	19	7 June 2023
	Parco Don Giovanni Scorza	40	32	16 June 2023
	Pineta Sacchetti *	331	231	27 June–8 August 2023
	Street-side trees in Saxa Rubra	41	39	10 June 2023
Giardino Aldo Tozzetti	7	7	7 June 2023	
Parco Tor Tre Teste	28	27	7 June 2023	
Tuscany region, Pisa	Tenuta San Rossore *	238	238	10 September 2023

2.2. Field Data Survey: Geographical Location of *Pinus pinea*

All the green areas with the presence of *P. pinea* of Rome are attacked by *T. parvicornis* (Figure 2). An in situ survey was conducted to create a reference dataset and to restrict the analysis to tree species affected by the infestation (*Pinus pinea*), excluding all others. Surveys were conducted between June and August 2023 at the selected sites (Figure 1 and Table 1). During each inspection, every stone pine in the chosen areas was classified according to the infestation status and georeferenced. A point shapefile was created where each point represents a tree classified as infested or healthy.

Figure 2. Examples of infested areas: (a) Villa Borghese, (b) Pineta Sacchetti, and (c) twig with *T. parvicornis*.

The fully digital data-recording methodology enabled the direct use of these data using QGIS 3.16.15 and the Google Earth Engine.

In this initial phase, the process was structured into several successive surveys, leading to visits to more areas than were ultimately chosen for the study. Indeed, it was necessary to assess the actual visibility of satellite images, overlapping the georeferenced data with the PlanetScope images (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Overlapping georeferenced points (each point represents a tree) and PlanetScope false-color images: (a) Villa Lazzaroni (excluded from the analysis) and (b) Villa Borghese (included in the analysis).

In addition, a significant number of areas were affected by the presence of dead or felled trees, which diminished the number of suitable trees available for analysis (Table 1). This reduction in tree density compromised the effectiveness of remote sensing in these regions. Consequently, any areas where canopy cover was thinned (e.g., trees along roadways or spaced too far apart) were excluded. This approach allowed for the selection of only proper areas for detailed analysis, thereby ensuring a sufficient sample size for combination with remotely sensed data. As the considered insect has infested all green areas of Rome (Latium Region), a control area was established in a non-infested area close to the city, with size and characteristics (e.g., uniformity of tree species) appropriate for the analysis: the Tenuta San Rossore, a section of the Regional Park of Migliarino, San Rossore, and Massaciuccoli, a protected area located in Tuscany, between the provinces of Pisa and Lucca. This Regional Park covers an area of 23,115 ha and includes a variety of natural environments, such as coastal areas, pine forests, woodlands, wetlands, and Lake Massaciuccoli (<https://www.parcosanrossore.org/pianificazione-e-governo-del-territorio/piani-di-gestione/> accessed on 10 October 2024). Due to its size and landscape diversity, the park is an important area for biodiversity conservation and for the protection of natural habitats typical of the Tyrrhenian coast. The park's area is 50% forested, dominated by pine forests (both *Pinus pinaster* Ait. and *Pinus pinea* L.) [37] that have not yet been infested by *T. parvicornis*. Approximately 230 plants were surveyed over an area of 10 ha.

2.3. PlanetScope Data

In the areas circumscribed in the field surveys, high-resolution satellite images were acquired to characterize the trees by calculating vegetation indices. In this study, we used PlanetScope nano-satellite images acquired between 15 July 2019 and 15 July 2023. These images were derived from the second generation of PlanetScope satellites (PS2.SD), which are available from 2019 and include 4 spectral bands and 8 quality bands. The 4 spectral bands are reported in Table 2.

The quality bands (Table 3) were used for cloud mask and noise correction [26,38]. The noise due to changes in sun angle depending on acquisition time was removed by calculating weekly composites by averaging all images acquired for each week [39].

Table 2. PlanetScope spectral bands.

Spectral Band	Wavelength
Blue	464–517 nm
Green	547–585 nm
Red	650–682 nm
NIR	846–888 nm

Table 3. PlanetScope quality bands.

Quality Band	Information
1	Clear mask
2	Snow mask
3	Shadow mask
4	Light haze mask
5	Heavy haze mask
6	Cloud mask
7	Confidence
8	Unusable data mask

Images were co-registered using the PlanetScope co-registration tool, which enables the spatial alignment of a series of images within a specified time series (<https://developers.planet.com/apis/orders/tools/> accessed on 20 August 2024). The order—and, thus, the co-registration, clipping, and downloading of the imagery—was performed in sequence for 21 study areas. This was important, as, to properly apply the co-registration tool, there had to be consistent overlap between different PlanetScope scenes; thus, small study areas were needed. The final resulting number of downloaded co-registered and clipped images was 30,481.

2.4. Vegetation Index Calculation

From the weekly composite PlanetScope images, we extracted the values of the four spectral bands corresponding to each georeferenced point. Then, the Renormalized Difference Vegetation Index (RDVI) (Equation (1)) was calculated based on previous studies [30,40,41].

$$RDVI = \frac{(NIR - R)}{(NIR + R)^{0.5}} \quad (1)$$

where R is the red band, and NIR is the near-infrared band. Although the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is the most commonly used index in vegetation studies [41,42], the RDVI is derived from the NDVI, reducing its sensitivity to soil effects (<https://www.nv5geospatialsoftware.com/docs/BroadbandGreenness.html#Renormal> accessed on 18 February 2024) and minimizing saturation effects [43]. Furthermore, the RDVI has been demonstrated to be efficient in terms of capturing subtle changes in forest conditions over time [44,45].

2.5. Infestation Detection

Depending on the specific objective, the analyses considered both groups of trees (i.e., treating areas as single entities) and individual plants. Area-level analysis proved more effective in comparing healthy and infested zones, as observing the diachronic trend at the single-tree level presented challenges. This complexity arises due to pixel variability, which is partially “smoothed” by the presence of multiple trees within an area [46]. In contrast, single-tree analysis was particularly useful for identifying discriminant values between healthy and infested plants. It focused on the index value within a specific, limited timeframe [47], during which the values of the two conditions were best differentiated. In the area-level analysis, the monthly RDVI average for both infested and healthy areas was calculated based on all trees within each area over the entire study period (2019–2023).

In the plant-level analysis, the summer average RDVI ($RDVI_{sua}$) values were calculated for the years 2020, 2021, and 2022, referring to the months of July and August, as, during these months, the difference between the spectral behavior of healthy and infested plants is higher. The year 2023 was excluded due to the absence of data for the considered period, and 2019 was also excluded, as the differences between healthy and affected plants were less significant. Then, the normal distribution (Equation (2)) of the $RDVI_{sua}$, was analyzed using a spreadsheet, to provide a statistical representation of the variability of this parameter.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where σ = standard deviation of $RDVI_{sua}$, and μ = mean of $RDVI_{sua}$.

3. Results

In the area-level analysis, the monthly average RDVI values for both healthy and affected areas (Figure 4) showed a decline throughout the spring–summer period of each year. Nevertheless, the RDVI trend in the control area differed significantly from that of the areas affected by *T. parvicornis*. Specifically, the control area did not exhibit the pronounced decline observed in the infested zones during the summer months, maintaining relatively stable photosynthetic activity levels.

Figure 4. Monthly average RDVI of infested area (shades of grey) and healthy area (blue).

The analysis of RDVI values in the infested areas revealed that the lowest average values recorded showed an increasing trend over time. Specifically, the minimum peak reached an average value of 26.6 in 2022, much better compared to the value of 21.9 in 2020.

In the single-plant level analysis, the normal distribution (Equation (2)) of $RDVI_{sua}$ presented a clear separation between healthy and infested areas (Figure 5).

Based on this evidence, some $RDVI_{sua}$ thresholds were tested through the construction of a confusion matrix (Table 4). The matrix assessed the classification accuracy of each threshold-based classification compared to the field-survey data. A threshold value of 33.1 optimized the classification accuracy, calculated using the overall accuracy (0.996), producer accuracy (0.999), and user accuracy (0.996). An RDVI threshold of 33.1 ensured the highest accuracy in distinguishing between affected and healthy plants.

Figure 5. Normal distribution of RDVI_{sua} of healthy and infested areas.

Table 4. Confusion matrix considering RDVI_{sua} = 33.1 as threshold.

Summer RDVI _{sua} Threshold = 33.1		Threshold Classification		
		Infested	Healthy	Total
Field survey classification	Infested	1596	1	1597
	Healthy	6	232	238
	Total	1602	233	1835

Overall accuracy = 0.996, producer accuracy = 0.999, and user accuracy = 0.996.

A visual evaluation of PlanetScope imagery also demonstrates temporal changes. In 2022, the areas dominated by *P. pinea* displayed a lower response in NIR bands (as shown by the darker red areas in Figure 6) when compared to 2019, suggesting healthier conditions in 2019 [48]. Additionally, the crown density appeared to have decreased over time (Figure 6).

Figure 6. False-color PlanetScope images (in the red channel is displayed the NIR band) of Villa Pamphili of 2022, 2020, and 2019. White circles indicate areas with the presence of pine trees.

4. Discussion

Monitoring insect infestations through remote sensing is a well-established practice [49–51]. Accordingly, in this research, we monitored insect infestation considering vegetation indices determined from high-resolution satellite data. The complexity of urban patterns poses a challenge for studying green spaces within densely built-up areas [52]. In this context, although PlanetScope images have been widely employed for vegetation monitoring [18,30,53], their spatial resolution (3 m) and temporal resolution (1 day) make

them very promising for use in studies focused on urban contexts. Compared to Sentinel-2 images, PlanetScope images allow for an increase in spatial detail of more than 10 times and a reduction in revisit time from 5 days to 1 day, with a historical series that reaches 2014 [54].

In detail, the spectral information provided in the PlanetScope data was used for the first time to test the utility of the RDVI index in monitoring *T. parvicornis*. The suitability of the index was evaluated to describe infestations [55], compared to other vegetation indices already used for this purpose, such as NDVI, EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index), EVI2, NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture index), and Modis ET (Modis Evapotranspiration time series) [56,57]. Aragonés et al. [58] demonstrated that the average NDVI trend for *P. pinea* peaks in the winter and declines in the summer, indicating a slowdown in plant activity during warmer months. The RDVI index shows a similar temporal trend to the NDVI, but, when comparing the RDVI values of healthy and insect-affected areas, the decrease between late spring and early autumn is significantly more pronounced in infested plants (Figure 4), which are profoundly debilitated, showing more accentuated minimum values. Analyzing a time span of 48 months—longer than other studies of this kind [59–62]—allowed for the identification of recurring trends. In particular, the distribution of the July/August RDVI averages (RDVI_{sua}) clearly distinguished healthy plants from infested plants, but the deterioration tended to decrease gradually over time. For instance, the lowest average peak index values (indicative of higher degradation) were 21.9 in 2020, 24.6 in 2021, and a minimum peak of 26.6 in 2022. This observed increase in lower peaks may be attributed to the extensive implementation of endotherapeutic treatments across the municipality of Rome since the autumn of 2020. Research conducted in Italy has demonstrated that endotherapy is the most effective method for managing pest invasion [59–61]. Additionally, this approach is particularly suitable for urban environments, as it minimizes public exposure to chemical agents [63].

The length of the considered observation period is one of the aspects that makes this research useful in supporting the management of *T. parvicornis* infestations in urban areas. Considering the reproduction periods of *T. parvicornis* [15,17], there are three ovideposition cycles within a year: between the second half of April and May, between July and early August, and between September and November. Correlating these periods with the vegetative cycle of *Pinus pinea* highlights the concomitance between vegetative stress and the insect's infestation, which significantly affects the plant's vitality compared to a non-infested tree (Figure 4).

A further element that supports the consistency of the results and the usability of the proposed approach for monitoring activities is the supplementation of remote-sensing data with in situ surveys. These surveys are useful for focusing the analysis on areas where infestation presence is known with certainty, thus allowing the spectral behavior of those areas to be studied in a targeted and limited way. This is particularly important in an urban context, where there is great heterogeneity in land cover and variability even within the tree cover, both in terms of plant placement and species diversity [64,65]. This can be problematic in areas with complex vegetation structures, where the signal from non-target species or underlying substrates (e.g., buildings, roads, or other ground cover) can overlap with the spectral signal from *P. pinea*. Through the georeferencing of trees using ground surveys, it was possible to accurately identify the pixels relating to *P. pinea* [32], enabling a deeper analysis of their spectral behavior. Another confounding factor is the great variability in the size and health status of pine canopies. Age, tree size, crown density, and environmental stressors can cause significant differences in spectral reflectance, even within a single species. For this reason, georeferenced pixel values were preferred over average canopy value, as the latter could introduce more noise into the remote sensing-data extraction [66].

Comparing the normal distributions of the RDVI_{sua} for the infested areas and the control area (with trees free of infestation and in good health), it was possible to define a threshold value of RDVI of 33.1, which can be used as a reliable criterion for separating

damaged areas from intact ones. In this sense, the index can be useful in supporting monitoring activities, providing preliminary information for identifying diseased trees with low implementation costs and high timeliness. Considering this value, it is possible to discriminate between healthy and diseased areas with an overall accuracy of over 99%. In any case, healthy trees belong to a natural and protected area (i.e., Parco Regionale Migliarino, San Rossore, and Massaciuccoli), and, consequently, the photosynthetic activity of these plants may already be better than that of plants in an urban area [67]. This result showed consistency not only due to the long observation period but also due to the size and heterogeneity of the study area considered, which goes beyond homogeneous pine forests in the natural environment [68] to focus on trees in the urban area [63].

Potential and New Challenges

As Senf et al. [69] observed in their review, field data constitute a crucial element in the study of forest insect disturbances, particularly in the context of remote sensing. For this reason, it is important to evaluate the efficacy of the treatments employed to control insect spread. Unfortunately, no comprehensive information on these treatments was available for this study. The municipality of Rome has conducted and continues to conduct endotherapy cycles in the most affected areas. However, complete information regarding the timing and modalities of these cycles is currently unavailable. Consequently, the interpretation of the results was also influenced by this deficiency. In addition to endotherapy, the *T. parvicornis* treatment guidelines [70] recommend crown thinning. This technique is employed to mitigate the proliferation of *T. parvicornis*. It is therefore pertinent to highlight that in instances where maintenance has been conducted appropriately, the trees in question have undergone a significant degree of thinning. In the absence of the insect, ordinary pruning would have been carried out and not extraordinary pruning, as was the case [71]. This would have resulted in a reduction in crown thickness, with all that this entails as previously discussed. This type of information is essential to better understand the results in more detail. More emphasis should be placed on regular data collection. The absence of a historical series, even for field data, represents a significant obstacle to the evaluation and effective utilization of these data.

Although remote sensing remains a fundamental tool for the study of tree health, it is important to acknowledge certain inherent limitations. First, although high-resolution images were employed in this study, it remains challenging to work on the scale of the individual tree. The canopy size of *Pinus pinea* can vary significantly, ranging from approximately 2 m in younger trees to 10–12 m in mature trees [72]. Using imagery with a spatial resolution of 3 m, single-tree analysis would be subject to significant errors, as accurately distinguishing individual canopies would be challenging. Overcoming this limitation would require the acquisition of very high spatial resolution spectral data, which currently necessitates specialized equipment, such as sensors mounted on drones. However, detailed monitoring at the single-tree scale still represents a major challenge for remote sensing techniques. In the future, once these limitations are addressed, the use of high-resolution vegetation indices could become a pivotal tool for precisely analyzing the activity and health conditions of individual trees [73].

Consequently, large areas are typically assessed as single entities [74]. Moreover, as remote sensing employs nadir images, only the crowns can be assessed when studying trees [48]. This ultimately gives rise to two issues. First, as in the case of *T. parvicornis*, if damage commences in the lower part of the crown, it will only be possible to discern the infestation at an advanced stage. Second, a reduction in reflectance resulting from the desiccation of the crown may be obscured by the reflectance of the background (if other species on the ground are present). Background is a confounding factor in the interpretation of remote-sensing results because it can alter the spectral signal. Elements such as soil, water, artificial structures, or other vegetation cover can reflect light in similar ways or overlap with the signal of the target of interest [75]. This overlap makes it difficult to isolate the spectral behavior of vegetation and can compromise the accuracy in identifying specific

conditions. In the future, by testing the use of different spectral indices and increasing the information obtained in the field, it would be possible to reduce the influence of the background, improving the reliability of the results.

5. Conclusions

Five main conclusions can be drawn from this study.

First, the use of PlanetScope imagery enabled the study of small urban areas due to its high spatial resolution. Moreover, the availability of daily data allowed for the collection of highly accurate information regarding the spectral responses of the analyzed areas. Even if PlanetScope imagery requires a paid subscription, the cost is relatively low compared to the operational advantages it provides. With an annual investment of approximately EUR 12,000, it is possible to access up to 30 million km² of imagery. While free options such as Landsat and Sentinel-2 are available, PlanetScope offers significant advantages in terms of spatial and temporal resolution, making it a valuable choice for projects requiring detailed and frequent monitoring. This balance between cost and enhanced capabilities highlights the practicality of PlanetScope for large-scale, high-resolution studies. The use of PlanetScope imagery for detecting *T. parvicornis* is a novel approach that has yielded promising results.

Second, ground-based georeferenced data were successfully integrated with remote-sensing techniques, enabling the extraction of precise information from satellite images in areas of interest. This method allowed for the analysis of the spectral responses of *P. pinea* alone, excluding other species in the area.

Third, the RDVI index proved to be effective in distinguishing between infested and healthy trees. Although previous studies on *T. parvicornis* in Italy utilized different indices, the application of the RDVI to this specific phenomenon yielded particularly satisfactory results.

Fourth, a threshold was identified to classify healthy versus infested plants. This threshold represents a valuable tool in the management of *T. parvicornis*, as it is easily applicable in various urban contexts.

To effectively counteract the invasion of *T. parvicornis*, further studies in this direction are necessary. Among future developments, it would be interesting to develop a technique to identify markers that allow for intervention before the plant dies. In this sense, sharing more information from stakeholders on the health of the plants before infestation and the timing of treatment cycles could enhance the interpretation of the phenomenon's dynamics. Continuing to conduct annual ground surveys will expand the volume of data and knowledge regarding the current state of the plants, as doing so is essential for refining remote sensing-based work and obtaining more accurate results.

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